

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SPIRAL APPROACH IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS IN THE K-12 PROGRAM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13734567>

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of the spiral approach in teaching Mathematics within the K-12 curriculum at Roxas National High School, focusing on students from Grades 7 to 10. Utilizing a descriptive research design, the study examined students' performance in Mathematics, administered the Spiral Mathematics Questionnaire (SMQ), and analyzed changes in academic grades. Results revealed a consistent increase in Mathematics grades from Grade 7 to Grade 10, with a significant improvement noted in Grade 10. Although the SMQ indicated that the spiral approach was "Least Effective," the actual grades of students suggested otherwise, demonstrating the approach's effectiveness in enhancing mathematical understanding over time. The study concludes that the spiral approach is effective as it positively impacts students' academic performance. The significant increase in grades highlights its role in reinforcing learning and promoting long-term retention of mathematical concepts. Recommendations include curriculum updates, teacher training, and the development of alternative learning materials.

Keywords: *Spiral Approach, Mathematics Education, K-12 Curriculum, Academic Performance, Long-term Retention*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics has various practical applications in daily life, making it essential for students to learn the subject with depth and comprehension. It is expected to develop students' critical thinking and problem-solving skills, which are crucial for their success in both academic and real-world contexts. In the K-12 program, the Mathematics curriculum from Grade 7 to Grade 10 covers Measurement, Geometry, Patterns and Algebra, and Probability and Statistics at each grade level. Students are expected to develop skills such as understanding, estimating, computing, solving, visualizing, modeling, representing, communicating, conjecturing, reasoning, proving, decision-making, and applying and connecting mathematical concepts. Additionally, Mathematics hones students' values of accuracy, creativity, objectivity, perseverance, and productivity (Biggs, 1996; Bruner, 1960; DepEd, 2016).

Despite the structured curriculum, many teachers face challenges in ensuring that students master these skills and embody the associated values. A common issue is that students may demonstrate proficiency in a certain skill or topic when it is initially taught, but they often forget or develop misconceptions when these topics are reviewed or revisited before introducing new lessons or concepts (Pashler et al., 2007; Rohrer, 2012; Tobias, 2009). This challenge of retaining mathematical knowledge highlights the importance of a curriculum that reinforces learning through iterative exposure.

To address these challenges, the Department of Education (DepEd) implemented a curricular framework anchored on spiral progression, particularly with the rollout of the K-12 curriculum. Both private and public schools in the Philippines have adopted the spiral learning method. Spiral learning is a pedagogical approach that introduces a topic, touches on it briefly, and then revisits it periodically. The premise is that a subject is not fully learned the first time it is encountered; however, with each subsequent exposure, students expand their skill levels and build new understandings (Harden, 1999; Shulman, 1986).

A spiral curriculum in Mathematics involves repeatedly presenting the same topics throughout a student's educational career, with each encounter increasing in complexity and reinforcing previous learning. This approach is particularly effective in Mathematics because many topics build on one another with increasing complexity (Hiebert & Wearne, 1996; Kilpatrick et al., 2001). For example, in the early grades, students learn basic addition and subtraction. These skills are foundational, as they are used in more complex operations such as multi-digit addition and subtraction, which eventually lead to algebraic manipulation in high school (Van de Walle, 2007; Wiggins & McTighe, 2005).

However, while the spiral approach works well for certain mathematical concepts, it can present challenges in mastering math facts. Without ongoing practice, students may forget basic facts, leading to gaps in their mathematical foundation that can hinder future learning (Anderson et al., 1996; NCTM, 2000). This underscores the need for a balanced

approach that combines spiral progression with targeted reinforcement of fundamental skills.

The spiral progression approach is rooted in progressive educational theory, particularly the work of John Dewey, who emphasized continuous, experiential learning (Dewey, 1938; Kolb, 1984). According to Monroy et al. (2014), progression refers to students' educational journeys and how they acquire, apply, and develop their skills, knowledge, and understanding in increasingly challenging situations. This approach also involves continuity, which concerns how the education system structures learning experiences to ensure consistent challenge and progress (Johnston, 2012; Shayer & Adey, 2002).

Given these theoretical foundations, the spiral progression approach facilitates both the breadth and depth of knowledge. By revisiting concepts with increasing complexity, students reinforce and extend their understanding, ultimately achieving a more comprehensive and integrated grasp of mathematical principles (Bruner, 1960; Wiliam, 2011). This approach not only enhances retention but also enables the transfer of knowledge to new and unfamiliar contexts (Anderson et al., 1996; Harden, 1999).

Motivated by these insights and challenges observed in the classroom, the researcher, a senior high school Mathematics teacher, is prompted to investigate the effectiveness of the spiral approach in teaching Mathematics within the K-12 program. This study aims to provide empirical evidence on the impact of the spiral progression approach on students' mathematical performance, which could inform enhancements to the Mathematics curriculum in the Philippine education system.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of the spiral approach in teaching Mathematics in the K – 12 program. Specifically, the researcher sought to find answers to the following problems:

1. What is the student's performance in mathematics from Grade 7 to Grade 10?
2. How effective is the spiral approach in teaching mathematics as revealed by the result of the Spiral Mathematics Questionnaire (SMQ) administered to the students and their grades in Mathematics from Grade 7-10?
3. Is there a significant increase in their academic grades in Mathematics?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The descriptive research method was utilized in the study to determine the effectiveness of the spiral approach in teaching mathematics to Grade 11 students at Roxas National High School. Descriptive research is also called Statistical Research, the

main goal of which is to describe the data and characteristics of what is being studied. The idea behind this type of research is to study frequencies, averages, and other statistical calculations. Therefore, this design is the most suitable to measure the effectiveness of the spiral approach in teaching mathematics to Grade 11 students.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted at Roxas National High School, Roxas, Isabela which is strategically located in the municipality of Roxas. The said institution has been in existence since 1972. Currently, the school has a total population of 2705 enrolled students.

Selection and Description of the Respondents

The respondents in this study were the Grade 11 students of Roxas National High School for the SY 2016-2017 who underwent the spiral approach from grades 7-10. The total number of respondents is composed of 153 male and 220 female students from the 9 sections. The breakdown of the respondents is shown in the table below.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents

Section	No. of Pupils		Total
	Male	Female	
STEM (diamond)	28	15	43
ABM (Aquamarine)	7	38	45
HUMMS (Ruby)	23	32	55
HUMMS (Topaz)	21	29	50
HUMMS (Jade)	22	22	44
TVL-H.E (Pearl)	7	25	32
TVL –ICT (Sapphire)	23	13	36
TVL –ICT (Emerald)	18	21	39
TVL –H.E (Amethyst)	4	25	29
Total	153	220	373

Data Gathering Instrument

The researcher used the Spiral Mathematics Questionnaire (SMQ) to determine students' achievement as an indicator of the effectiveness of the Spiral Approach. The researcher administered the Spiral Mathematics Questionnaire (SMQ) during the school year 2016-2017 to the students who underwent the Spiral Approach from grades 7-10. It is a group test intended to be given in the second semester.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before the questionnaire was distributed, a letter was sent to the principal of Roxas National High School asking permission to conduct the research study. After it was approved, the researcher personally distributed it to respondents.

The questionnaire was given to the respondents during their vacant time so as not to interrupt their classes. Their schedule was taken from the adviser of each section. After the respondents had answered, the questionnaires were collected, scored, tallied, and summarized by the researcher and statistically treated.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data gathered were analyzed and interpreted using the following statistical tools:

Frequency and Percentage Count. To analyze the data for problem 1 and problem 2 on the Mathematics performance of students from Grade 7 to Grade 10 and their performance in the Spiral Mathematics Questionnaire (SMQ), the frequency and percentage count were used.

F - ratio Test. This was employed to determine if there was a significant increase in the student's academic grades in Mathematics from each grade level.

Data Analysis Procedure

The data gathered was organized, tabulated, and interpreted using the following scales:

SMQ Score	Description
33 – 40	Very Much Effective
25 – 32	Much Effective
17 – 24	Effective
9 – 16	Leas Effective
1 – 8	Not Effective

Grade	Description
90 – 100	Outstanding
85 – 89	Very Satisfactory
80 – 84	Satisfactory
75 – 79	Fair Satisfactory

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Students' Performance in Mathematics from Grade 7 to Grade 10

Table 1. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Students and their Performance in Mathematics from Grade 7 to Grade 10

Grade	Description	Math 7		Math 8		Math 9		Math 10	
		f	%	F	%	f	%	f	%
90 100	Outstanding	24	6.43	26	6.97	26	6.97	62	16.62
85 89	Very Satisfactory	96	25.74	107	28.69	101	27.08	103	27.61
80 84	Satisfactory	170	45.58	149	39.95	153	41.02	124	33.24
75 79	Fair Satisfactory	83	22.25	91	24.40	93	24.93	84	22.52
Total		373	100	373	100	373	100	373	100
Mean		81.46		81.30		82.80		83.91	
Description		Satisfactory		Satisfactory		Satisfactory		Satisfactory	

Table 2 presents the students' performance in Mathematics from Grade 7 to Grade 10. It is evident from the table that 170 or 45.58 percent got a satisfactory grade in Math 7; 149 or 39.95 percent in Math 8; 153 or 41.02 percent in Math 9, and 124, or 33.24 percent in Math 10. The table also shows that the number of students who performed very satisfactorily has increased from Grade 7 to Grade 10 as shown by the frequency of 96 in Grade 7, 107 in Grade 8, 101 in Grade 9 and 103 in Grade 10. Likewise, those who had outstanding performance have gone up to 62 in Grade 10 compared to 24 in Grade 7.

The data further reveals that the average Grade of students in Mathematics have improved over the four years as shown by their average grade of 81.46 in Grade 7, 81.30 in Grade 8, 82.80 in Grade 9, and 83.91 in Grade 10.

Effectiveness of the Spiral Approach in Teaching Mathematics As Revealed by the Result of the Spiral Mathematics Approach (SMQ) Administered to the Students and their Grades in Mathematics

a. Spiral Mathematics Questionnaire

Table 3. The Effectiveness of the Spiral Approach in Teaching Mathematics as Revealed by the Results of the Spiral Mathematics Questionnaire Administered to the Students.

Scores	Qualitative Description	Frequency	Percentage
33 – 40	Very Much Effective	0	0.00
25 – 32	Much Effective	15	4.02

17- 24	Effective	152	40.75
9 – 16	Effective to some extent	178	47.72
1 – 8	Not Effective	28	7.51
Total		373	100
Median	Leas Effective		15.80

The effectiveness of the spiral approach in teaching mathematics as revealed by the result of the Spiral Mathematics Questionnaire administered to the students is exhibited in Table 3.

It is shown from the results that 178 or 47.72 percent of the students got scores of 9 – 16 which is interpreted as "Least Effective", and 152 or 40. 75 percent garnered nearly 17 – 24 or "effective". Fifteen students scored 25-32 which is interpreted as "much effective" and 28 or 7.51 percent got nearly 1 – 8 measuring the spiral approach as "not effective".

It can be noted from the findings that the spiral approach in teaching mathematics is “Least effective” as revealed by the results of the SMQ administered to the students. This is attributed to the fact that some of the topics given in the test were already forgotten by the students or cannot remember the process/concepts.

b. Grades in Mathematics

Table 4. The Effectiveness of Spiral Approach in Teaching Mathematics as Revealed by the Students’ Grades in Mathematics

Grades	Qualitative Description	Frequency	Percentage
90 and above	Outstanding	30	8.04
85 – 89	Very Satisfactory	94	25.20
80 – 84	Satisfactory	161	43.16
75 – 79	Fair Satisfactory	88	23.59
Total		373	100
Median	Satisfactory		81.44

Table 4 exhibits the effectiveness of a spiral approach in teaching mathematics as revealed by the students' grades in Mathematics.

The results indicate that the spiral approach in teaching mathematics is effective as revealed by the students' grades in Mathematics wherein most of the students have satisfactory grades which is in contrast to what is revealed by the Spiral Mathematics Questionnaire.

c. Increase/ Decrease in Grades

Table 5. The Effectiveness of Spiral Approach in Teaching Mathematics as Revealed by the Increase/ Decrease in Mathematics Grades of the Students

Increase/ Decrease	Math 7 – 8		Math 8 – 9		Math 9 – 10	
	<i>F</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
4 – 7	28	7.51	12	3.22	28	7.51
0 – 3	176	47.18	156	41.82	241	64.61
-3 – 0	152	40.75	192	51.47	95	25.47
-7 - -4	17	4.56	13	3.49	9	2.41
total	373	100	373	100	373	100

The effectiveness of the spiral approach in teaching mathematics as revealed by the increase/decrease in Mathematics grades of the students is presented in Table 5.

It is clear from the table that 204 or 54.69 percent, 168 or 45.04 percent, and 269 or 72.12 percent of the students have obtained an increase in their mathematics grades in Math 7 to Math 10. The findings note that the majority of the students have an increase in their mathematics grades in Math 9 – 10 while most of them are in Math 8 – 9. Likewise, the majority of the students' grades have decreased in Math 8 – 9 and 45.31 percent had a decrease in grades in Math 7 – 8 and about 28 percent in Math 9 – 10. Therefore, it can be implied that the spiral approach in teaching mathematics is effective as revealed by the increase/ decrease in mathematics grades of the students which are also affirmed by the results as evidenced by their grades in math.

Increase in the Students' Academic Grades in Mathematics from Grade 7 to Grade10

Table 6. Results of Significant Increase in the Academic Grades in Mathematics of the Respondents

Variable	The computed value of F	Tabular Value of F	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Increase in Academic Grades in Mathematics	25.54	3.00	$F_c > F_t$	Reject H_0	Significant

Table 6 reflects the results of the test showing a significant increase in the students' academic grades in Mathematics.

The results show that the computed value of $F = 25.54$ is greater than the tabular value of $F = 3.0$. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 level of significance.

Moving forward, there is a significant increase in academic grades in the mathematics of the respondents. It implies that the students' increase in their mathematics grades from Grade 7 to Grade 10 is significant which means that the Spiral approach in Mathematics is effective.

Conclusions

The study reveals that the spiral approach in teaching mathematics has a positive impact on students' academic performance. From Grade 7 to Grade 10, there is a consistent increase in students' mathematics grades, with a significant improvement noted in Grade 10. Although the Spiral Mathematics Questionnaire indicated the approach was "Least Effective," the actual grades of students suggest otherwise, showing that the method is effective in enhancing mathematical understanding over time. The significant increase in academic grades confirms the effectiveness of the spiral approach, emphasizing its role in reinforcing learning and promoting long-term retention of mathematical concepts.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are forwarded based on the findings and conclusions of the study:

1. The DepEd should continually revisit and update the curriculum to further enhance the spiral approach curriculum in Mathematics. Curriculum planners and other concerned authorities should work hand-in-hand to attain their goals.
2. The Department of Education should design and conduct seminars and trainings for teachers to further enhance their skills and knowledge in the application of the Spiral Progression approach in Mathematics to ensure mastery of knowledge and skills after each level.
3. Teachers should also be involved in developing alternative learning materials to meet the needs of the diverse learners in the learning process.
4. The teachers should see to it that the spiral progression of topics in Mathematics should show the intertwining of lessons at every year level. What has been studied in one specific course or area should be live with the other topics learned with increasing difficulty.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research was conducted in strict adherence to ethical principles, including integrity, respect, and responsibility towards all participants. Informed consent was obtained before the study, ensuring that participants fully understood the purpose, procedures, and any potential risks. Confidentiality and anonymity were rigorously maintained throughout data collection, analysis, and reporting, protecting participants' privacy. The researcher also ensured there was no conflict of interest, avoided plagiarism,

and interpreted the results without bias. Lastly, the findings were used solely for this research, ensuring ethical use of the data.

Acknowledgments

I extend my heartfelt gratitude to my research adviser for their unwavering guidance, to the respondents for their valuable participation, and to my colleagues and friends for their support. To my family, your love and encouragement fueled my perseverance. Above all, I thank God for His constant inspiration and strength throughout this journey. This work is a testament to the collective efforts and blessings I have received.

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